

Quinoline Derivatives. Part II. Pyrazolinoquinolines.

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In the present investigation an attempt has been made to fuse a pyrazole ring system in the 2:3-position of a quinoline for obvious pharmacological reasons.

Aromatic *o*-nitroaldehydes condense with phenylmethylpyrazolones in presence of sodium acetate to give condensation products of the type (I).

On reduction these substances do not smoothly pass to the corresponding quinolines. The product from *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (I, R = R' = H) gives a tetrahydroquinoline (II).

The reduction of the nitro compound obviously proceeds through a hydroxylamino compound (III) because from the mixed hydrochlorides of the crude reduction product the substance (III) can be isolated. McClusky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1575) has reported the formation of a similar quinoline oxide in the reduction of ethyl *o*-nitrobenzoylacetoacetate.

The substance (I) dissolves in acids and also in alkalis, a behaviour in keeping with its structure and gives a monohydrochloride with hydrochloric acid whilst a pyrazolinoquinoline is expected to form a dihydrochloride. The same substance is obtained if the reduction is carried with either aluminium amalgam or zinc dust and acetic acid or alcoholic hydrochloric acid.

The condensation product with nitropiperonal or nitroveratric aldehyde on reduction is converted to the related amine (IV), which

can be cyclised to the pyrazolinoquinoline (V) by heating with anhydrous sodium acetate in a current of hydrogen. It is noteworthy that whatever reducing agents are employed the substance (IV) is produced in every case and no simultaneous ring formation occurs (*cf.* Armit and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 827, *et seq.*, who found that an *ortho*amino unsaturated ketone cyclises to a quinoline in presence of acetic acid but not in presence of hydrochloric acid). Therefore, it seems that the amino group is in *trans* position with respect to the ketonic grouping.

The substance gives a *trihydrochloride* which may be due to the addition of a molecule of hydrogen chloride at the double bond. Even the nitro compound which is of a striking colour becomes nearly colourless in presence of hydrochloric acid due no doubt to the destruction of conjugation owing to the addition of hydrogen chloride at the double bond.

The respective structures assigned to the compounds have been tested by means of their absorption spectra which confirmed the conclusions drawn.

EXPERIMENTAL.

o-Nitrobenzylidene-1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone.—An intimate mixture of phenylmethylpyrazolone (3.5 g.), *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (3.0 g.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (3.5 g.) was heated to 150° for 2 hours with stirring. The pasty mass soon solidified and assumed

a dark red colour. It was washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in bright red needles, m.p. 162° , yield 3 g. (Found: N, 13.5. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires N, 13.68 per cent).

Reduction with zinc dust and acetic acid.—(a) The nitro compound (1 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (20 c.c.) by heat and the solution was reduced with zinc dust in small quantities till the dark red solution turned pale yellow. The hot solution was filtered, hydrochloric acid (d 1.16, 2 c.c.) added and diluted to 100 c.c. with water and the solution saturated with ammonium chloride, when a pale yellow substance (0.6 g.) crystallised out. It was crystallised from hot methanol containing hydrochloric acid, m.p. 251.52° . [Found: N*, 13.1; Cl, 11.2 (by precipitation with silver nitrate in alcoholic solution). $C_{17}H_{17}ON_3$, HCl requires N, 13.3; Cl, 11.3 per cent].

(b) The nitro compound (0.5 g.) dissolved in moist ether (100 c.c.) was reduced with aluminium amalgam during 24 hours, when the dark red solution became pale pink. Removal of the solvent furnished a substance which had m.p. 252° after crystallisation from methyl alcohol and hydrochloric acid and showed no depression on admixture with the product described under (a).

(c) The nitro compound (0.5 g.) dissolved in alcohol (20 c.c.) was reduced with zinc dust and hydrochloric acid and after the removal of the solvent the product was worked up as under (a) when the same substance as described under (a) and (b) was obtained.

Isolation of the base (II).—The crude hydrochloride obtained in the reduction of the nitro compound with zinc dust (1 g.) suspended in water (50 c.c.) was treated with ammonia (d 0.8, 10 c.c.) when a clear solution resulted. On concentration of the solution in *vacuo* at 60° a colourless substance (A) (0.8 g.) crystallised out and from the filtrate chloroform extracted a dark coloured pasty substance (B). The substance (A) was crystallised from a mixture of benzene-ligroin in glistening needles, m.p. 142° . (Found: C, 72.7; H, 6.4; N, 15.1. $C_{17}H_{17}ON_3$ requires C, 72.8; H, 6.1; N, 15.1 per cent).

The dark coloured pasty substance (B) was triturated with petroleum ether and a brown coloured solid was obtained. It crystallised from hot benzene (charcoal) in colourless needles, m.p. $101-102^{\circ}$. (Found: N*, 14.4. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14.3 per cent). It is probably the substance (III), since it reduced ammoniacal silver nitrate instantaneously and after heating with acids gave the test for a diazotisable amine.

Condensation of nitropiperonal with phenylmethylpyrazolone.—

A mixture of nitropiperonal (4 g.), phenylmethylpyrazolone (3.6 g.) and fused sodium acetate (3 g.) was heated at 135° for 2 hours. The product after treatment with water was well washed with boiling alcohol and crystallised from hot acetic acid in red silky needles, m.p. 199° , yield 4 g. (Found: N*, 11.9. $C_{18}H_{13}O_5N_3$ requires N, 12.0 per cent). The nitro compound (1 g.), dissolved in hot acetic acid (30 c.c.), was treated with small quantities of zinc dust in such a manner as to keep the solution boiling gently till the solution became pale yellow. It was filtered and treated with hydrochloric acid (d 1.16), diluted with water to 80 c.c. and treated with ammonium chloride when a pale yellow substance (0.6 g.) separated. Crystallised from methyl alcohol-hydrochloric acid it came out as delicate colourless needles, m.p. 243° . Reduction of the nitro compound with aluminium amalgam also furnished the same product. (Found: N*, 9.8; Cl, 24.0. $C_{18}H_{15}O_3N_3$, 3 HCl requires N, 9.8; Cl, 24.7 per cent). The substance showed the presence of a diazotisable amino group.

The *hydrochloride* (1 g.) in water (100 c.c.) was treated with ammonia till it dissolved completely. The solution was concentrated in *vacuo* at 50° when a colourless crystalline substance separated which darkens in contact with air. It crystallised from hot alcohol in stout needles, m.p. 186° . (Found: C, 67.1; H, 5.3; N*, 13.1. $C_{18}H_{15}O_3N_3$ requires C, 67.3; H, 4.7; N, 13.1 per cent).

The *base* (1 g.) was well mixed with fused sodium acetate (3 g) and was heated in a current of dry hydrogen at 186° for a few minutes and then at 150° for 1 hour. The product, well washed with water, was crystallised from hot alcohol (charcoal) in pale yellowish needles, m.p. 185° , mixed m.p. with the amine $155-170^{\circ}$, yield 0.02 g. (Found: C, 71.2; H, 4.5; N*, 13.71, 13.92. $C_{18}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires C, 71.3; H, 4.3; N, 13.86 per cent). The substance does not show the presence of an amino group and gives a picrate.

The product of the condensation of nitroveratric aldehyde and phenylmethylpyrazolone conducted at 145° was isolated as in the previous cases. It crystallised from hot dilute acetic acid in brilliant red silky needles, m.p. 183° . (Found: N*, 11.1. $C_{19}H_{17}O_5N_3$ requires N, 11.4 per cent).

The nitro compound (4 g.) dissolved in hot acetic acid (100 c.c.) was reduced with zinc dust till the solution became pale yellow. The filtered solution was concentrated to 20 c.c. in *vacuo* and then diluted with water and a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid.

On saturation with ammonium chloride, the hydrochloride crystallised, which was recrystallised from amyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid in colourless needles, m.p. 226°, yield 2.3 g. [Found: N*, 9.5, 9.6; Cl, 23.2 (by precipitation). $C_{19}H_{19}O_3N_3 \cdot 3HCl$ requires N, 9.4; Cl, 23.8 per cent].

The grey coloured base (1 g.), isolated as in the previous case, did not give a sharp m.p. even after repeated crystallisations from benzene and other solvents, indicating that partial cyclisation had occurred. The crude base was mixed with sodium acetate and heated at 150° for 1½ hours. The product after treatment with water crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in pale yellow needles, m.p. 215°, yield 0.05 g. (Found: N*, 13.2. $C_{19}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 13.2 per cent).

The absorption spectra of the quinolines (V, $R=R'=OMe$, and $R=R'=O_2CH_2$) numbered as I and II respectively in the curve, that of IV (numbered as III) and that of I (numbered as IV) were taken in a concentration $M/10000$ in chloroform. The spectroscopic results show that the curves I and II are similar in character whilst IV differs markedly from both I and II. The curve III of the amino compound is again different from I, II and IV.

FIG. 1

* Analyses marked ' * ' were done by the micro method.

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